

ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON NOTCHED COMPRESSION OF HIERARCHICAL NANOENGINEERED AEROSPACE COMPOSITES STUDIED BY X-RAY MICROTOMOGRAPHY

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ABSTRACT

Hierarchical nanoengineered composites were fabricated via reinforcement of aerospace-grade carbon fiber/epoxy laminates in their failure-prone interlaminar regions with vertically aligned carbon nanotubes, in an architecture termed “nanostitching.” Motivated by previous studies reporting *ex situ* strength and toughness enhancements for nanostitched laminates in standard environments, this study investigates environmental effects on quasi-isotropic laminates subjected to open-hole compression (OHC) and featuring localized nanostitch reinforcement near the hole. Traditional standardized *ex situ* strength tests were conducted across various hygrothermal conditions. We find that -55°C/DRY and 100°C/DRY environments correspond to ultimate strength increases of 2.6% and 5.9%, respectively, for nanostitched laminates over the baseline; however, room temperature/50% relative humidity (RT/50% RH) and 100°C/WET conditions exhibited no ultimate strength change. For all conditions, OHC failures were identified to be multimodal and brittle. In an effort to characterize strengthening and toughening mechanisms associated with nanostitch, the 100°C/DRY condition was further examined to correlate *ex situ* strength improvement with 3D damage progression characteristics, employing high-resolution lab-based X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) to non-destructively observe damage micro-mechanisms in a relatively large field-of-view (mm-scale). Forming an interrupted loading/ μ CT scanning campaign, baseline and nanostitched specimens were initially scanned in the as-manufactured state, then loaded in a conventional mechanical test apparatus to load steps of 70%, 90%, and 95% of baseline OHC strength, in between which intermediate μ CT scans were performed upon unloading and removal from load apparatus. In both baseline and nanostitched laminates, 0° split matrix cracks were found similarly to be dominant matrix damage mechanisms, with slight delamination occurring at laminate corners, which appears consistent with the sudden brittle failures observed *ex situ*. Future analyses will examine higher load steps and additional hygrothermal conditions to further elucidate nanostitch effects on damage micro-mechanisms and thus strength improvement, as a vital step toward optimization and prediction of emerging multiscale architecture mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite laminates comprised of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) have become ubiquitous in modern high-performance aerospace structures, as they possess significant advantages over traditional engineering materials, including relatively high, tailorable mass-specific

in-plane stiffness and strength. Conversely, relatively inferior out-of-plane properties associated with matrix weakness often yield premature, poorly understood complex failures that limit broader adoption and restrict current possibilities for structural design improvements [1–3]. Damage progression in CFRPs, which generally encompasses a spectrum of modalities, interactions, and sequences across multiple material and structural scales, exhibits broad sensitivity to loading configuration, rate, and environment, as well as laminate morphology, manufacturing defects, and load-path discontinuities (*e.g.*, holes, free edges, ply drops, etc.) [1,2,4–10]. Particularly, temperature and moisture-level are primary environmental conditions that influence progressive matrix damage micro-mechanisms—such as ply-ply interlaminar separations known as delaminations and intra-ply matrix cracking, which commonly manifest early during pre-ultimate failure—and therefore the overall laminate mechanical response. Generally, the polymer matrix is the origin of environmental effects on laminate properties, since the hygrothermally sensitive polymer influences mechanical properties of both the matrix and the fiber/matrix interfacial bond; in contrast, the carbon fiber has relatively high thermal stability at standard service temperatures and does not absorb moisture [11–13]. At low temperatures, the polymer exhibits higher stiffness, strength, and brittleness; however, at high temperatures, the polymer experiences increased viscoelasticity and elevated ductility as it nears the glass transition temperature (T_g). In parallel, elevated moisture content can induce plasticization during water uptake and consequently decrease the T_g , promoting enhanced ductility. Compared to the standard room conditions in which most mechanical tests are performed, high temperatures and moisture levels typically degrade laminate mechanical properties and are associated with differences in progressive damage nucleation and propagation [14–17]. Additionally, hygrothermally induced residual stresses can also occur during environmental condition changes (relative to cure conditions) in the absence of loading due to property mismatches between the fiber and thermosetting polymer matrix in both the coefficient of thermal expansion and the coefficient of hygroscopic expansion [1,6,18,19].

Motivated by mitigating dominant failure micro-mechanisms like matrix cracking and delaminations that are observed widely via traditional damage characterizations, various solutions aimed at mechanical enhancement of conventional microfiber/polymer laminates have emerged in the form of hybrid/hierarchical technologies, which add nano- or microscale constituents for supplementary reinforcement. Appearing more broadly often due to simpler fabrication, hybrid composites may feature added microscale constituents in the form of 1D auxiliary microfibers for additional reinforcement—*e.g.*, secondary short microfibers aligned in the thickness direction (Z-pinning [20], stitching [21], tufting [22]), continuous fibers woven across multiple laminae (3D weaving [23]), and unidirectional (UD) non-carbon continuous microfibers [24]—and/or interleaving for additional interlaminar toughness [9,25,26]. One characteristic feature of micro-constituent additions is that there is typically a clear property trade-off: out-of-plane and/or interlaminar properties may be augmented (primarily to counter delaminations) but are traded off against degradation of in-plane properties, due to the microscale nature of the added constituents and their potential to disrupt, damage, or dilute UD laminae. To circumvent property compromise, a recent nanoscale approach to out-of-plane reinforcement of weak interlaminar regions using aligned carbon-nanotubes (A-CNTs)—called “nanostitching”—in a multiscale hierarchical composite has improved both in- and out-of-plane properties across several epoxy-based UD CFRP prepreg systems. Mechanical testing of nanostitched laminates has found strength, toughness, and fatigue improvements from the extremely lightweight nanostitch architecture [27–32], which can additionally enable desired structural multifunctionality due to superior CNT electrical and thermal conductivities [33,34]. Particularly, in standard ambient open-hole compression (OHC) testing that typically induces multimode failure including sub-laminate buckling via delamination, nanostitch has improved static strength by over 10% [27]. Additionally, Guzman de Villoria et al. [27] reported a stiffness reduction for both baseline and nanostitched specimens that is depicted as a decrease in the OHC stress-strain curve slope at ~30%–50% of the baseline ultimate strength. This suggests incipience of a significant subcritical damage event since the loading curve is highly linear just prior; however, this change in mechanical response was not investigated further for progressive damage correlation [27]. Furthermore, in addition to these prior damage characterization limitations, testing of nanostitch efficacy in various hygrothermal

environments, such as those commonly encountered by aircraft structures—*e.g.*, temperatures ranging from slightly below -50°C to above 100°C [1], is critical but currently unknown.

Traditional characterizations of damage progression are widely acknowledged to be insufficient, relying on practical *ex situ* observational techniques that can be limited spatially to 2D or quasi-3D (2D with depth information), or limited temporally to a *post-mortem* state. A key problem is sectioning to expose damage surfaces, which can have the effect of altering the diffuse damage state in unquantified ways. However, X-ray micro-computed tomography (μCT) has emerged as a valuable modern technique for non-destructive, direct 3D observation of damage progression with sub-micron resolution throughout a material volume [35]. Lab-based μCT tools are well-suited for *ex situ* characterizations during interrupted loading, in which specimens are cyclically loaded then unloaded for μCT scanning, during which damage mechanisms may slightly close [36]. Considering that lab-based tools can accommodate relatively large specimens, as well as thermal chambers, 3D progressive damage behavior in CFRP has been investigated via load-interrupted μCT in several studies, allowing standardized property measurements to be correlated with high-resolution morphological observations of failure mechanisms [37–41]. Regarding nanostitch, it is noted that in all prior experimental characterizations of progressive damage effects induced by nanostitch, damage was visualized typically with high-resolution exterior 2D methods (*e.g.*, scanning electron microscopy (SEM)) and/or lower-resolution μCT [30,32], such that failure micro-mechanism understanding is still insufficient for rational optimization and prediction of nanostitch mechanical effects.

Thus, we study here the nanostitch and environmental effects on composite OHC failure, using *ex situ* progressive X-ray μCT to reveal non-destructively the complex 3D damage progression vital to mechanistic understanding of strengthening and toughening, as well as future nanostitch optimization and prediction of laminate strength change.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

In this section, the following topics are described: the fabrication of nanostitched laminate specimens for OHC, the test method for standard environmental OHC, the methodology and parameters for μCT scanning, and the techniques for μCT volumetric image analysis.

Following ASTM D6484, $[0/90/\pm 45]_{2S}$ quasi-isotropic laminates comprised of aerospace-grade Hexcel AS4/8552 carbon fiber/epoxy prepreg were fabricated. A-CNTs (multi-walled) were synthesized on 30 mm x 40 mm Si wafers in a 2" tube furnace (Lindberg/Blue M) using atmospheric chemical vapor deposition, achieving a height of $20 \pm 5 \mu\text{m}$ and an areal density of $\sim 1 \text{ vol.}\%$ after ~ 60 s of growth time. Following a delamination step at the end of the CVD process to promote wafer/forest separation, the A-CNT forests were then transferred manually onto UD prepreg surfaces, integrating one forest into each specimen's interlaminar region, following Refs. [29,32]. Note that each nanostitch forest center was manually aligned with a given OHC specimen hole center. The laminates (300 mm x 300 mm) were then autoclave-cured under vacuum according to manufacturer specifications: 6.9 bar(g) of autoclave pressure at $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 110°C , hold for 60 min, heat again at $2^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 180°C , hold for 120 min, cool down at $3^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 60°C and vent autoclave pressure, let cool to ambient temperature. As shown in Fig. 1, autoclave pressure compacts the nanostitch to a final height of 7–10 μm .

OHC specimen geometry and the mechanical test setup with the Zwick Z100 loading apparatus are shown in Fig. 2. All holes were fabricated via orbital drilling and inspected via X-ray contrast radiography to check for delaminations, and all machined edges were polished. For wet-testing conditions, specimens were conditioned to moisture equilibrium, which was reached after 63 days and defined as achieving a daily weight change of less than 0.02%. Prior to loading, each specimen was surface-fitted with a thermocouple and maintained at temperature inside the Z100 thermal chamber for 3–5 min. Failure testing at a displacement rate of $\sim 2 \text{ mm}/\text{min}$ was performed for six specimens per environment for OHC strength property calibration. The following environmental conditions were

tested: room temperature (23°C)/50% relative humidity (RT/50% RH), -55°C/DRY (~0% RH), 100°C/DRY, and 100°C/WET.

Figure 1: Scanning electron micrograph of a representative nanostitched laminate cross-section, showing the nanostitch filling a 45°/90° interlaminar region and conforming to ply surface roughness.

Figure 2: OHC test and analysis overview: (left) *ex situ* environmental OHC test setup, and (right) specimen test-section geometry (length is 220 mm, thickness is 2 mm) marked with μ CT scan region.

Subsequently, an interrupted loading/ μ CT scanning method was performed by loading additional specimens in a selected environment to ~0%, 70%, 90%, and 95% of OHC baseline strength, and then unloading specimens at each load step for X-ray μ CT of one hole side (Figs. 2–3). High-resolution μ CT volumetric images with 1 μ m voxel size and a relatively large composite field-of-view (mm-scale) comprised of 6 individual smaller scans were acquired in widestitch mode with a ZEISS Xradia 520 Versa, while also leveraging a high-aspect ratio tomography operating mode to minimize certain related scan artifacts by optimizing the angular distribution of projections. Other key μ CT parameters

were as follows: 80 kV X-ray source energy, 5 s exposure time, and 3001 projections over an angular range of -94° to 94° . In Fig. 4, representative raw scan data from a baseline specimen is exhibited to give a glimpse of scan quality and auto-stitching seams generated by ZEISS reconstruction software.

Figure 3: Standard-sized OHC specimen positioned inside of lab-based μ CT tool prior to high-resolution, large field-of-view scanning of one side of the open hole.

Figure 4: Sample 3D renderings of an unsegmented AS4/8552 baseline volumetric composite image from lab-based μ CT. In (a)–(c), the same sample is depicted with different points-of-view and transparencies: (a) 2D radiograph captured through-thickness (in-plane location marked on 3D rendering), (b) transparent side view of 3D reconstruction showing seams from ZEISS automated scan stitching, and (c) opaque perspective view of 3D volume rendering.

ImageJ and Avizo software were then used in image analysis to pre-process (brightness/contrast, cropping, and bit depth scaling) and semi-automatically segment μ CT damage data, respectively. Avizo (FEI) commercial software was used to perform analysis and segmentation of the 3D reconstructed scan volumes, by using a 3D region-growing algorithm to segment matrix damage voxels exhibiting gray values that (i) fit within an appropriate user-specified gray value range (damage gray values are close to black) and (ii) are connected spatially via other eligible voxels to a user-specified seed point. Damage existing in regions located approximately greater than 30 μ m away from the notch edge was analyzed in order to achieve accurate and consistent region-growing results, which accounts for inevitable imaging artifacts due to propagation-based phase contrast present near the specimen edges. For consistency, the same gray value range corresponding to damage was standardized across all μ CT volume images, since they feature the same fiber/matrix constituent materials.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the following topics are presented for baseline and nanostitched laminates: *ex situ* environmental OHC ultimate strength properties and 3D matrix damage progression up to 95% of the baseline OHC strength.

As shown in in Fig. 5, OHC ultimate strength testing in various environments reported the following improvements in nanostitched vs. baseline laminate specimens: none at RT/50% RH, 2.6% at -55°C/DRY, 5.9% at 100°C/DRY, and none at 100°C/WET. Thus, nanostitch appears to show the strongest effects during brittle failure modes (embrittlement here typically via cold and/or dry) when matrix ductility/toughness is minimized. Note that dry T_g is 200°C and wet T_g is 154°C for the epoxy used here, as reported by Hexcel product data. In OHC of multiaxial laminates, degraded matrix properties generally promote early fiber microbuckling and delamination. In Fig. 6, representative *post-mortem* failure visualization is presented for both baseline and nanostitched specimens.

Figure 5: *Ex situ* OHC ultimate strength (σ_{OHC}) magnitudes (mean and standard error) for baseline (“REF”) and nanostitched (“NANO”) laminates subject to various hygrothermal conditions. The standard ambient condition is reported as room temperature (RT) and ~50% relative humidity (RH).

Figure 6: Representative *post-mortem* failure regions following RT/50% RH OHC testing of baseline and nanostitched specimens. The catastrophic final damage state extends to a wide region surrounding the hole, with an overall mixture of delaminations, 0° split matrix cracks, and translamellar cracks observed similarly in both baseline and nanostitched laminates.

For improved mechanistic understanding, additional baseline and nanostitched specimens at $100^\circ\text{C}/\text{DRY}$ were μCT imaged after unloading at each increasing load step (corresponding load curves shown in Fig. 7). In Fig. 8, 3D renderings of progressive matrix damage near one hole edge are shown for $100^\circ\text{C}/\text{DRY}$ baseline and nanostitched specimens, specifically showing progression from 70% to 95% of baseline OHC strength. Similar in both specimens, 3D damage states are dominated by intralaminar matrix splitting in 0° plies; though, 2D virtual cross-sections (Fig. 9) reveal that these cracks also form micro-scale delaminations in the baseline outer plies at laminate corners, whereas nanostitched does not typically exhibit precisely this same multimodal damage. Overall, the precise strength improvement mechanism via nanostitch is not yet captured here. However, *ex situ* calibration load-displacement curves for $100^\circ\text{C}/\text{DRY}$ specimens are \sim linear up to failure, indicating minimal subcritical damage, so significant damage differences are expected closer to ultimate failure, as delamination initiation has been observed to be delayed until high loads in related research of sub-laminate-scaled CFRP OHC [42].

Figure 7: Step-wise *ex situ* OHC loading curves for (a) one baseline and (b) one nanostitched specimen each conditioned at $100^\circ\text{C}/\text{DRY}$; specimens were immediately unloaded after reaching each peak load (legend) in order to be μCT -scanned. “Adjusted displacement” refers to rigid translation of curve along the x-axis to minimize grip slippage effects when comparing curves of increasing peak load. σ_{OHC} refers to the *ex situ* calibration OHC ultimate strength magnitude for the baseline laminate.

Figure 8: 3D matrix damage progression near one side of hole in 100°C/DRY (a–c) baseline and (d–f) nanostitched laminates. Matrix damage, found to be primarily intralaminar here, was segmented in μ CT scans for loads of 70%, 90%, and 95% of OHC baseline strength; damage color is presented according to its host ply: blue for 0° ply damage and yellow for 45° ply damage. Note that other salient OHC damage mechanisms such as fiber microbuckling and fiber kink bands are not shown here, but are the topic of future studies.

Figure 9: Matrix damage progression near a hole edge depicted in 2D tomograms corresponding to 100°C/DRY (a) baseline and (b) nanostitched laminates at the unloaded (0%) and 95%-strength load steps; tomogram orientations in 3D space are shown with respect to 3D renderings. Zoomed-in insets (red outline) show a potential difference in slight damage progression near the interlaminar regions: nanostitch generally redirects delaminations to just inside the intralaminar region. Note that nanostitch regions are not observable in μ CT due to similar X-ray attenuation properties versus neat epoxy.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A-CNTs were embedded into matrix-rich interlaminar regions of aerospace-grade composite laminates for strength and toughness enhancements via progressive damage suppression/alteration. OHC tests were performed in various hygrothermal environments to assess broad significance of A-CNT effects on in-plane notched compressive strength via delamination resistance. For a selected hygrothermal condition, X-ray μ CT enabled rich mechanistic insight into strength property behavior via progressive matrix damage visualization, which is ultimately a key step toward nanostitch optimization and advancement of currently limited failure modeling. Future work will include expanding the environmental conditions considered, damage imaging nearer to failure to identify precisely the environmental and nanostitch effects on complex multimodal CFRP failure, and characterization of other OHC damage mechanisms such as fiber microbuckling and fiber kink bands.

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